

oxime group. This is further corroborated by the higher pK value (12.37) of compound *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline (B) which may be due to the presence of methyl groups in *N*-phenyl ring.

The pK_{OH}^H value of the compound (C), i.e. *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine is found to be 13.01 which is higher than that of the compound *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)aniline. It is known that the electron density at the α -position of naphthalene is higher not only than the one at the β -position but also than the one at a carbon atom of the benzene ring, hence for the *N*-(1-naphthyl) derivative (C) the pK_{OH}^H value is higher as compared to *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)aniline.

The stability sequence of metal complexes formed by *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxylamine and *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline has been found to be $Cu^{II} > UO_2^{II} > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Co^{II} > Cd^{II}$ and that of *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine as $UO_2^{II} > Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Cd^{II}$.

Schiff bases are known to have chemotherapeutic activity against tubercule bacilli and other bacteria as well as against skin fungi⁴. The presence of azomethine linkage in compounds has been known to decrease the toxicity considerably^{5,6}. Hence *in vitro* antitubercular screening of these compounds was carried out against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* ($H_{87}R_v$) by the method of disperse culture technique using Kirchner's medium containing Tween-80 as dispersing agent. It is observed that *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxylamine and *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine are inactive, while the activity shown by *N*-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline is 12.5 mg ml⁻¹.

The anticoagulant activity of these compounds is evaluated by employing *in vitro*, Dale and Laidlaw technique⁷. The *in vitro* test was carried out using rabbit's whole-blood. Normal clotting time was first determined, using a capillary technique with twenty blood samples drawn from marginal ear vein of the animal. In order to test the anticoagulant activity of the compounds, the freshly drawn sample was first mixed with the test compound (3-4 mg) in a glass vial and mixed gently. The capillary was then quickly filled with the blood sample and the clotting time was determined. Results are given in Table 2. The normal clotting time was found to be 2.5 \pm 0.5 mins.

For compound (A), pK_s could not be evaluated due to negligible separation at lower pH. For compound (B), $\log K_2$ values in case of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} and for compound (C), $\log K_2$ values in all cases except UO_2^{II} , could not be evaluated, since there was early precipitation resulting in insufficient data.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES
Temp. = 30 \pm 0.1°, μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

	H ⁺	UO ₂ ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}
(A) <i>N</i> -(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxylamine							
$\log K_1$	12.08	10.90	12.28	10.73	8.71	8.87	7.93
$\log K_2$	10.85	—	10.56	9.30	—	—	—
(B) <i>N</i> -(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline							
$\log K_1$	12.37	10.87	11.25	10.31	9.50	10.06	8.40
$\log K_2$	9.41	9.50	9.87	8.85	8.08	—	—
$\log K_3$	3.19	—	—	—	—	—	—
(C) <i>N</i> -(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine							
$\log K_1$	13.01	11.66	11.38	10.26	9.18	10.81	9.15
$\log K_2$	9.36	10.23	—	—	—	—	—
$\log K_3$	2.17	—	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2

Compd.	Clotting time min
(A) <i>N</i> -(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxylamine	3.5 \pm 1.0
(B) <i>N</i> -(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline	4.0 \pm 1.0
(C) <i>N</i> -(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine	2.5 \pm 0.5

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Potentiometric Studies on Complexes of Bivalent Metal Ions with *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-3-aminopyridine and *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-methoxy-5-acetylaminoaniline and Evaluation of these Reagents for Anticoagulant Activity

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POTENTIOMETRIC studies have been carried out on metal chelates of Mg^{II} , Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-3-aminopyridine and *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-methoxy-5-acetylaminoaniline. The

dissociation constants of the reagents and the formation constants of their metal chelates have been determined by Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹ at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1 *M* in dioxan-water (75 : 25, v/v) medium.

Experimental

The reagents (A) *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-3-aminopyridine and (B) *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-methoxy-5-acetylaminoaniline were prepared by condensing equimolar ethanolic solutions of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde and the respective amines. The products were repeatedly crystallised to obtain pure samples. The purity was tested by tlc and elemental analysis. The experimental details and computational methods are the same as described in our earlier publication².

Calculations: From the titration data \bar{n}_A values were determined and plotted against *B* (pH meter readings) to obtain values of pK_1 and pK_2 . These were further corroborated by straight line plots of $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ and $\log (2-\bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A-1)$ vs *B*, respectively. From the metal titration curves, \bar{n} and *pL* values were calculated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding *pL* values to get the formation curves of the metal complex ion equilibria. From these plots values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were evaluated. They were further corroborated by straight line plots of $\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})$ and $\log (2-\bar{n})/(\bar{n}-1)$ vs *pL*, respectively. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 M$							
	II ⁺	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Mg ^{II}
(A) <i>N</i> -(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-3-aminopyridine							
$\log K_1$	9.43	9.13	6.35	6.60	6.05	4.30	3.16
$\log K_2$	4.86	6.70	—	—	—	—	—
(B) <i>N</i> -(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-methoxy-5-acetylaminoaniline							
$\log K_1$	10.05	10.26	6.91	6.86	6.70	4.30	4.35
$\log K_2$	2.25	—	—	—	—	—	—

Results and Discussion

The pK_{OH}^H value of (A) *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-3-aminopyridine (9.43) is lower than that of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)aniline (9.72). In the case of compound (A), the aromatic sextet of π -electrons is less perfect than in benzene, because nitrogen in pyridine is more electronegative than carbon, and it tends to withdraw electrons of the π -cloud towards itself making the ring electron-deficient and thus resulting in lower pK_{OH}^H value, while the pK_{OH}^H value of (B) *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-methoxy-5-acetylaminoaniline (10.05)

is higher than that of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)aniline (9.72). The OCH_3 group in the compound (B) has unshared electron pair on the oxygen atom. This would interact with the π -orbital of the *N*-phenyl ring exerting +M effect resulting in higher pK_{OH}^H value of (B). In addition, $NHCOCH_3$ group is also electron-donating, and as a result the pK_{OH}^H value of the compound (B) is higher than that of *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)aniline.

The order of the stability constants for the ligand (A) is $Cu > Co > Ni > Zn > Cd > Mg$, and that for (B) is $Cu > Ni > Co > Zn > Cd > Mg$.

In order to explore the possible relationships between $\log K$ values and certain fundamental properties of the metal ions, stability constants ($\log K_1$) of the metal ion chelates were plotted against atomic number of elements (Fig. 1). The stability

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_1$ vs atomic number: (x) A and (O) B.

constants of chelates increase steadily to reach a maximum at copper and fall from zinc to cadmium. It also shows that they form a roughly triangular form, with apex at Cu^{II} and base extending from Mg^{II} to Cd^{II} . Similar relationship was observed by Irving and Williams⁴.

The reported reagents are good chelating agents and they form chelates with Ca^{II} ions like EDTA. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to investigate their *in vitro* anticoagulant properties. The anticoagulant activity of these reagents was evaluated following Dale-Laidlaw technique⁵. The *in vitro* test was carried out using rabbit's whole blood. Normal clotting time was first determined using capillary technique with twenty blood samples drawn from marginal ear vein of the animal. The freshly drawn sample was mixed with the test compound (3–4 mg) in a glass vial. The capillary was then quickly filled with the blood sample and the clotting time determined. The clotting time was found to be 2.5 ± 0.5 and 2.5 ± 0.2 min for compounds (A) and (B), respectively.

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Oxidation Studies of *N*-Salicyloylflavanone Hydrazones with Selenium Dioxide

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RECENTLY, Barton *et al.*¹ reported that treatment of ketone hydrazones, oximes and semicarbazones with benzeneselenic anhydride regenerated the parent ketones. However, the corresponding aldehyde derivatives when treated similarly, yielded^{2,3} the azo and nitroso compounds. Formation of the products largely varies with the substrates, reagents and reaction conditions.

In the present investigation, we have studied the oxidation of some *N*-salicyloylflavanone hydrazones⁴ (1a-f) in acetic acid (90%, v/v) medium employing selenium dioxide, which has rarely been used as an oxidant for nitrogenous functions. This reaction afforded two major products, viz. salicylic acid (2) and flavones (3a-f) along with flavanone azines (4a-f) in comparatively poor yields. The probable reaction routes leading to the formation of different products are given in Schemes 1 and 2 and the results of the investigation are recorded in Table 1. The proposed reaction mechanism shows the following possibilities: (i) the formation of flavones is also possible by dehydrogenation of the starting materials followed by removal of nitrogen-

- a; R = R' = R'' = H
- b; R = R'' = H, R' = OCH₃
- c; R = CH₃, R' = R'' = H
- d; R = CH₃, R' = OCH₃, R'' = H
- e; R = H, R' = R'' = OCH₃
- f; R = CH₃, R' = R'' = OCH₃

ous moiety, *i.e.* without the intermediacy of flavanones, and (ii) flavanone azines may also be formed by condensation of flavanone hydrazones (first step of Scheme 1) with flavanones (Scheme 2).

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries using sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Structure of the compounds were checked by elemental analysis. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra on a Varian EM 360 spectrophotometer at 60 MHz.

Oxidation of N-salicyloylflavanone hydrazone (1a): *N*-Salicyloylflavanone hydrazone (3.5 g, 0.008 mol) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and to it added a clear solution of selenium dioxide

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF *N*-SALICYLOYLFLAVANONE HYDRAZONE WITH SELENIUM DIOXIDE

Hydrazone	M.p. °C	Oxidation product*	M.p. °C	Yield %
1a	224	3a	99	18.4
		4a	256-58	10.9
1b	212	3b	157-58	20.9
		4b	254-55	8.8
1c	218	3c	120-22	19.8
		4c	242-43	12.5
1d	209	3d	170	19.5
		4d	252-53	8.7
1e	195	3e	155	22.0
		4e	256d	9.3
1f	193	3f	189	21.7
		4f	275d	11.6

*Salicylic acid (2) was isolated in all the six cases studied.

(2.2 g, 0.019 mol) in distilled water (4.0 ml), slowly with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h on a steam-bath and then cooled, and the grey selenium metal (1.2 g) separating was filtered off. The solution was diluted with